

Synthesis of 9,11-dodecadien-1-yl acetate from aleuritic acid

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9,11-Dodecadien-1-yl acetate (7), the sex pheromone of *Diparopsis castanea* (red bollworm moth) has been synthesised from aleuritic acid (1).

9,11-Dodecadien-1-yl acetate (7, *E*:*Z* = 80:20) is the most potent of the sex pheromones produced by the *Diparopsis castanea* (red-bollworm moth), a major cotton pest in south eastern Africa¹. Several workers² have prepared the compound from different starting materials, often employing complex reaction sequences. We herein report a simplified synthesis of 7 from azelaic acid aldehyde (2), one of the periodate oxidation products of *threo*-aleuritic acid (1). Compound 1 can be easily obtained from alkaline hydrolysis of shellac³.

(1)

(2) R=H

(3) R=CH₃

(4)

(5)

(6)

(7)

Results and Discussion

Methyl ester of azelaic acid aldehyde (3) was prepared by periodate oxidation of 1 followed by esterification of the resultant azelaic acid aldehyde (2) with diazomethane⁴. Then, methyl ester of azelaic acid aldehyde (3) was coupled with prop-2-enyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (4) to get methyl 9,11-dodecadienoate (5) through a simplified Wittig reaction via a solid/liquid transfer process. The solid/liquid

transfer process is reported to be a versatile one in the Wittig synthesis of dienes with higher yields⁵. Compound 5 was then reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to obtain an alcohol (6), which was finally treated with Ac₂O/pyridine to get 9,11-dodecadien-1-yl acetate (7). The *E*-*Z* ratio of 7 was found to be nearly one by hplc.

Experimental

Ir and nmr spectra were recorded respectively on Bomem-100 spectrophotometer and Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz) instrument (using TMS as internal standard). The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by tlc.

Prop-2-enyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (4): A mixture of allyl bromide (4.8 g) and triphenylphosphine (10.4 g) taken in toluene (15 ml) was refluxed with stirring for 3 h. The salt obtained was separated by filtration under reduced pressure. The crystals were then washed with toluene and dried (13.8 g, 91%).

Methyl 9,11-dodecadienoate (5): A mixture of 4 (3.83 g), methyl ester of azelaic acid aldehyde (3; 1.86 g), potassium carbonate (1.4 g) and toluene (30 ml) was refluxed while stirring for 4 h. The mixture was then filtered and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was recuperated with ether to precipitate the remaining triphenyloxide, if any. The ethereal solution was filtered, evaporated and the resultant residue was chromatographed on a silica gel column with petroleum ether: ethyl acetate (95:5) to afford the pure diene as a liquid (1.7 g, 81%), ν_{max} 2926, 2858, 1745 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.10–1.70 (10H, m), 2.06 (2H, quartet like m), 2.33 (2H, t), 3.66 (3H, s), 4.96 (1H, d), 5.12 (1H, d), 5.35–6.20 (3H, m); *m/z* 210 (27.5%, M⁺), 183 (18.9%, M-CH=CH₂), 179 (11.2%, M-31).

9,11-Dodecadien-1-ol (6): The methyl ester (5; 1.1 g) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (0.25 g) in dry THF (25 ml) at ambient temperature for 24 h and the residue obtained after usual work-up was chromatographed over

a silica gel column. Elution of the column with pet. ether : ethyl acetate (80 : 20) afforded the product as a liquid (0.81 g, 85%), ν_{\max} 3366 (OH), 2928, 1455 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.1–1.8 (12 H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_n$), 2.12 (2H, quartet like m), 3.65 (2H, t), 4.95 (1H, d), 5.10 (1H, d), 5.40–6.60 (3H, m); m/z 182 (13.1%, M^+), 164 (3.7%, M-18), 154 (2.5%), 136 (2.1%), 121 (9%).

9,11-Dodecadien-1-yl acetate (7) : Compound 6 (0.75 g) was stirred with pyridine (8 ml) and acetic anhydride (8 ml) for 6 h at ambient temperature and left overnight. Then it was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was sequentially washed with dil. HCl, NaHCO_3 solution (5%), and water and dried over Na_2SO_4 . Removal of the solvent and purification of the residue over a column of silica gel yielded the product as a liquid (0.78 g, 83%), ν_{\max} 2924, 2860 and 1736 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.15–1.70 (12H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_n$), 2.04 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.08 (2H, quartet like m), 4.06 (2H, t), 5.02 (1H, d), 5.15 (1H, d), 5.52–6.70 (3H, m); m/z 224 (8.1%, M^+), 165 (7.6%), 164 (17.5%).

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